

On the Stochastic Geometry Modeling and Optimization of Multi-Tenant Network Slicing

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Abstract—Network virtualization and softwarization techniques are key-enablers of the novel Network Slicing concept. Network slicing introduces new business models such as allowing telecom providers to lease a virtualized slice of their infrastructure to tenants such as industry verticals, e.g. automotive, ehealth, factories, etc. In this paper, regarding this concept, we propose a new analytical framework, based on stochastic geometry theory, to model realistic RANs that leverage the business opportunities offered by network slicing. Moreover, we formulate a 2-Tenant optimization problem in order to optimally allocate transmit power and bandwidth (i.e., a slice of radio access resources) to the users of each infrastructure tenant. Numerical results are illustrated to validate our proposed solution in terms of potential spectral efficiency.

Index Terms—Cellular Networks, Stochastic Geometry, Network Slicing, Optimization

I. INTRODUCTION

Advanced service requirements from vertical industries necessitate a novel design of 5th generation (5G) mobile networks, in order to increase the revenues of telecom providers and network operators. To address this challenge, the introduction of new technologies, such as network programmability and virtualization, is required. In this context, the novel definition of network slicing [1], [2] encompasses such new requirements and constitutes an enabler for potential economical benefits. They are forcing infrastructure providers to open their networks to tenants, a solution that provides incentives for monetizing the availability of isolated and secure (virtualized) network slices. In particular, the resource management of the radio access network (RAN) is one of the most challenging aspects that needs to be dealt with behind such concept. The available resources of the RAN air interface can be sliced at multiple levels: in frequency, time, and power domains. Slicing the network at this level of granularity requires to account for the cellular network topology, the other-cell interference and the radio channel conditions experienced by the users of every single tenant.

To solve this never-addressed and challenging issue, we leverage the mathematical tool of stochastic geometry and the theory of point processes [3]. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first attempt towards the design of an automated RAN slicing admission control and resource allocation scheme that provides throughput guarantees in the RAN, where the cellular network topology and the other-cell interference are taken into account. The main research contributions made

by the present paper can be summarized as follows: i) we derive a new mathematical formulation of the network spectral efficiency with the aid of stochastic geometry tools, which explicitly accounts for the interplay among the transmit power of the cellular base stations (BSs), the available spectrum and the deployment densities of cellular BSs and mobile terminals (MTs) of each tenant, ii) we formulate a feasible 2-Tenant network slicing optimization problem based on the convexity property of proposed utility function, which could provide a optimal resource allocation scheme in the heterogeneous cellular networks.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

A. Cellular Network Modeling

The BSs are modeled as points of a homogeneous Poisson point process (PPP), denoted by Ψ_{BS} , of density λ_{BS} . The MTs of each tenant are modeled following a different homogeneous PPP, denoted by Ψ_{T_i} , of density λ_{T_i} , for $i = 1, 2$. Ψ_{BS} , Ψ_{T_1} , and Ψ_{T_2} are assumed to be independent. The MTs are served by the BS providing the best average received power on the downlink channel. All the other BSs transmitting over the same frequency spectrum act as interfering BSs (i.e., full-frequency reuse is considered). Each BS transmits with constant power. P_{tot} denotes the total power budget of each BS. Each BS transmits in a spectrum of total bandwidth B_{tot} . The percentage of transmit power and bandwidth used by T_i are denoted by P_{T_i} and B_{T_i} for $i = 1, 2$, respectively, such that $P_{T_1} + P_{T_2} \leq P_{tot}$ and $B_{T_1} + B_{T_2} \leq B_{tot}$. The spectrum bands used by T_1 and T_2 are non-overlapping and, thus, no inter-tenant interference is available. The other-cell interference (among BSs of the same tenant transmitting over the same spectrum) is, on the other hand, taken into account.

B. Potential Spectral Efficiency

For ease of notation, we formulate the PSE for a generic tenant whose MTs constitute a PPP of density λ_T , and whose BSs allocate transmit power P and bandwidth B . Based on the new definition of coverage probability proposed in [4], the exact mathematical expression of the PSE is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \text{PSE}(P, B, \lambda_T) = & B \log_2 (1 + \gamma_I) \frac{\lambda_{BS} L \left(\frac{\lambda_T}{\lambda_{BS}} \right)}{1 + L \left(\frac{\lambda_T}{\lambda_{BS}} \right) \Upsilon(\gamma_I, \beta)} \\ & \times \left[1 - \exp \left(-\pi \lambda_{BS} \left(\tau_A \frac{P}{B} \right)^{2/\beta} \left(1 + L \left(\frac{\lambda_T}{\lambda_{BS}} \right) \Upsilon(\gamma_I, \beta) \right) \right) \right] \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where $\tau_A = (k\gamma_A N_0)^{-1}$ and:

$$L\left(\frac{\lambda_T}{\lambda_{BS}}\right) = 1 - \left(1 + \frac{1}{3.5} \frac{\lambda_T}{\lambda_{BS}}\right)^{-3.5} \geq 0 \quad (2)$$

$$\Upsilon(\gamma_I, \beta) = {}_2F_1\left(-\frac{2}{\beta}, 1, 1 - \frac{2}{\beta}, -\gamma_I\right) - 1 \geq 0 \quad (3)$$

where γ_I is the reliability threshold for successfully decoding a data packet and γ_A the reliability threshold for detecting the presence of the serving BS during the cell association phase. $\beta > 2$ is the path-loss exponent, and N_0 is the noise-power spectral density.

III. PROBLEM FORMULATION

In this section, we formulate an optimization problem and identify the optimal transmit power and spectrum to be assigned to each tenant so as to obtain the maximum requested spectral efficiency.

The mathematical formulation of PSE expressed in (1) is proved to be jointly concave in both transmit power and bandwidth. Therefore, in order to investigate the optimal allocated resources for 2-Tenant network slicing scenario with the given rate threshold R_{T_1} and R_{T_2} , we formulate the following problem:

$$\begin{aligned} \max_{\substack{P_{T_1}, P_{T_2}, \\ B_{T_1}, B_{T_2}}} & \text{PSE}(P_{T_1}, B_{T_1}, \lambda_{T_1}) + \text{PSE}(P_{T_2}, B_{T_2}, \lambda_{T_2}) \\ \text{s.t.} & \text{RATE}(P_{T_1}, B_{T_1}, \lambda_{T_1}) \geq R_{T_1} \\ & \text{RATE}(P_{T_2}, B_{T_2}, \lambda_{T_2}) \geq R_{T_2} \\ & P_{T_1} + P_{T_2} \leq P_{\text{tot}}, B_{T_1} + B_{T_2} \leq B_{\text{tot}} \\ & P_{T_1}, P_{T_2}, B_{T_1}, B_{T_2} \geq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where average rate can be expressed by PSE based on the following: $\text{RATE}(P, B, \lambda_T) = \frac{\text{PSE}(P, B, \lambda_T)}{\lambda_T}$.

IV. NUMERICAL AND SIMULATION RESULTS

In this section, we illustrate numerical results based on the exact analytical framework of PSE in (1), which was proposed according to stochastic geometry.

In Fig. 1, the PSE in Eq. (1) is validated against Monte-Carlo simulations as a function of decoding threshold for different densities of MTs, which is computed by $\lambda_T = 1/\pi R_{MT}^2$. Note that here we represent the density of MTs by the average radius in meter. In Fig. 2, we solve the convex optimization problem in (4) by using MATLAB with "fmincon", and we plot the obtained optimal solutions of allocated resources for Tenant-1 as a function of the corresponding rate threshold. The Brute-Force search is applied for validation.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have introduced a new tractable analytical framework of PSE based on stochastic geometry, and the proposed mathematical approach is in good agreement with Monte-Carlo simulations. Based on the convexity of PSE, we analyze the system-level spectral performance for 2-Tenant network slicing optimization problem. We believe that the

Fig. 1: Potential spectral efficiency vs decoding threshold for different densities of MTs (R_{MT} is average radius in meter). Markers: Monte-Carlo Simulations. Solid lines: Mathematical Frameworks.

Fig. 2: Optimum allocated resources versus rate threshold for Tenant-1. Markers: Brute-Force search. Solid lines: fmincon.

proposed methodology is suitable for generalization with more than 2 tenants, which is left for future work.

VI. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work is supported in part by the European Commission through the H2020-ETN-5Gaura project under grant 675806.

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